

Alliance Simplified Template (Funding Application Stage) Rubric

Version 1.0

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**Digital Research
Alliance** of Canada

**Alliance de recherche
numérique** du Canada

The purpose of this rubric is to provide a general framework for assisting with the development of good quality DMPs (Data Management Plans). This rubric is ideally intended for use alongside the [Alliance Simplified Template \(Funding Application Stage\)](#) developed specifically to help researchers in meeting DMP requirements imposed by funders, and which can be found and utilized within the [DMP Assistant](#) Platform.

The Simplified Template consists of five primary questions spanning key topics across the research lifecycle. Additional guidance is available within the template both under 'Introductory Guidance' and the corresponding guidance provided with each question. This rubric offers additional support and guidance to researchers and those assisting with the development of their DMPs by expanding and providing clarity for each question along with performance criteria, as well as a basic scoring method which is intended to help identify when certain areas and aspects of a DMP may benefit from, or require, additional attention.

Scoring:

- **2 Indicates a complete response** that addresses all relevant performance criteria with adequate detail. The answer is tied to the discipline and/or methodology, as appropriate.
- **1 Indicates a partial or incomplete response.** Some of the performance criteria may not be fully addressed or contextualized to the project.
- **0 Indicates a missing or inadequate response.** Answers are either absent or their relevance is unclear.
- **N/A Indicates that the response is not applicable.** An answer to the question does not apply.

This rubric was developed by members of the Digital Research Alliance of Canada's Data Management Planning Expert Group (DMPEG) rubric working group¹. The working group would like to extend our gratitude to members of the Tri-Agencies, who took the time to review this rubric and provide constructive feedback.

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Template Question	Performance Criteria	Reviewer Comments	Score
<p><i>What considerations will you take into account with respect to ethical, legal, or commercial issues?</i></p> <p>Describe any applicable ethical, legal, or commercial considerations related to your project and data. This includes research involving Indigenous communities and knowledges, human subjects, legal and commercial considerations/agreements, partnerships or data with a high level of risk associated with it.</p>	<p>Demonstrates consideration of any applicable policies, terms of use, and/or other agreements relating to ethical, legal, or commercial issues, with notable examples including:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Tri Council Policy Statement: Ethical Conduct for Research involving Humans (TCPS2); • research ethics board requirements, and any other policies or agreements applicable relating both to the project and the data used; • commercial or business implications such as Memorandums of Understanding (MOUs), intellectual property agreements or licensed data, which may consist of data agreements, or health data considerations. <p>If any new technology is being developed, clearly explains if any technology transfer will occur.</p>		
	<p>Information is provided on how research data will be managed and safeguarded, especially if data contains sensitive information, and notably if research data contains any human participant data.</p>		
	<p>Identifies if any research will be conducted relating to Indigenous communities, rights holders, and knowledges.</p> <p>If yes, explains how the research will honour and support the tenets of Indigenous data governance and sovereignty, including the collective benefit, ethical responsibility and ownership and control of data for the indigenous community, key constituencies, and knowledges.</p>		

	<p>If any principles or guidelines are being used to support indigenous data sovereignty, such as The First Nations Principles of OCAP or CARE Principles for Indigenous Data Governance, provide details.</p>		
Subtotal: _____			
<p><i>What data will you collect or otherwise bring into your project under this plan?</i></p> <p>Describe the data that will be collected, generated, and/or acquired.</p>	<p>Fulsome description of the type(s) of data that will be generated collected, and/or acquired (e.g., image data, textual data, numerical data, audiovisual), as well as formats, making note of proprietary/non-proprietary format(s) (e.g., CSV, jpg).</p>		
	<p>Provides an estimate of the size of the data (e.g., GBs; TBs), taking into account all data types and file versioning.</p>		
	<p>Indicates whether data will be sensitive in nature, and/or whether data will involve Indigenous communities and/or knowledges and information.</p>		
Subtotal: _____			
<p><i>How will you document data for future re-use or validation?</i></p> <p>Describe how you will document your data to ensure that it is easily read and interpreted correctly throughout the research process.</p>	<p>Provides a clear plan for documentation and metadata as appropriate for methods and data. As applicable, provides information on any metadata standards that will be implemented, and the documentation and metadata processes are outlined with sufficient clarity to support the full data lifecycle.</p>		

<p>If applicable, specify any data and/or metadata standards that are being used to support your research project.</p>	<p>Describes any hierarchies, codebooks, data dictionaries, readme files, lab and/or field notes, code, syntax, or file naming conventions, as applicable.</p>		
<p>Subtotal: _____</p>			
<p><i>How will data be stored, accessed and worked with?</i></p> <p>Describe both where and how data will be stored, accessed, and worked with during the active phases of your research including as applicable:</p> <p>all versions of data (e.g., raw, master, analytic)</p> <p>All activities (e.g., data collection, processing, analysis, dissemination)</p> <p>All software and platforms</p> <p>Who requires access, including security measures (e.g., Investigators, research staff, collaborators, partners)</p> <p>How data will be backed up to prevent data loss</p>	<p>Provides a clear description of where and how the data will be stored during the active phases of the research project, including a comprehensive list of any software, versions and platforms.</p>		
	<p>Gives sufficient detail on backups, including where they are, how they are done, how long they are kept, what the frequency is, and how they can be accessed.</p>		
	<p>Describes specifically who (or which roles) will be granted permissions to access the data and provides details on what data they are allowed to access (e.g., all data, only certain data, de-identified versions of data).</p>		

	Describes security measures and information on data protection in the case of sensitive data. Identifies if there are any restrictions on access of data, and/or if individuals require ethics approval to work with any raw or sensitive data.		
Subtotal: _____			
<p><i>How will data be managed, discoverable, and accessible for the long term?</i></p> <p>Describe plans for long-term management of your data <u>after the active phases</u> of your research have concluded including data deposit and sharing.</p> <p>Consider and describe as applicable plans for:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - all versions of data deposited (raw, master, analytic, published) - All activities (e.g., curation, preservation, ethical compliance, publishing etc.) - All software and platforms (e.g., data repositories) 	<p>Long term data stewardship refers to the retention, deposit and/or preservation of data after completion of the active phases of a research project.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Retention refers to the management of research data after completion of the active phases of a research project. ● Deposit refers to the selection and deposit of research data into a data repository. ● Preservation refers to activities that ensure research data selected for long term storage or deposit will be accessible over time. <p>Indigenous data sovereignty:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● As applicable, if the research and its data includes any aspects of Indigenous culture, knowledges and/or information, a clear succession plan and demonstrated commitment to Indigenous data sovereignty is provided 		
	If human participant data is collected, information is provided on what mechanisms are in place (and appropriate) to protect participants' confidentiality.		
	Identifies how data can be stored for long term data stewardship and access while ensuring compliance with any relevant ethics and/or participant consent.		

RETENTION

Provides a clear description of which data, if any, will be selected for long term retention, as well as a rationale for these decisions (e.g., compliance with funder and/or institutional requirements or policies such as data deposit into a repository, ethics compliance, recommendations or requirements from publishing journals, results verification, future analyses by same team and/or future researchers, teaching and learning purposes, data use agreements, community or industry partners ownership of data).

Explains any retention timelines for data and provides clear rationale for why data will not be stored beyond the active phases of the project (e.g., data could be easily recreated, data may be subject to data use agreements or requires transferring to commercial/industry partners, data may be highly sensitive).

Describes how data selected will be prepared for long term storage, including any quality assurance, normalizing, and/or de-identification activities that will occur.

Addresses if there are copies of data being retained but not deposited with a steward (such as a data repository), and provides information on where it will be stored (e.g., publisher platforms, research team or institutional local storage).

	Provides details on any processes used for data cleaning and/or format changes, including any file format considerations to ensure long term availability (e.g., proprietary/non-proprietary files, coding languages, scripts and/or programs and versions).		
	<i>DEPOSIT</i>		
	Explains how the data will be made discoverable, accessible, and reusable. Data deposit involves the publication of research data through the deposit of research data into a data repository (e.g., research specific repositories, institutional repositories, or generalist repositories). Data published within a repository may provide a persistent identifier, promoting FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) data principles and can be linked to publications through a data availability statement.		
	Describes any pertinent information about the chosen steward (e.g., repository) such as whether a persistent identifier is assigned for the dataset, and if the dataset record is searchable and explains reuse terms for each dataset.		
	Provides information on whether research data deposited will be subject to embargoes, and if it will be open access or deposited with restrictions. Details are provided on whether data will be shared or otherwise made available for reuse and under what conditions (e.g., human participant data ethics considerations, any applicable licenses or terms of use).		

	<p>For data that will be deposited, details are provided on any processes used for data cleaning and/or format changes, including any file format considerations to ensure long term availability (e.g., proprietary/non-proprietary files, repository recommendations/requirements, coding languages, scripts and/or programs and versions).</p>		
	<i>PRESERVATION</i>		
	<p>Preservation refers to ensuring accessibility to research data in perpetuity. Repositories may provide preservation services, and information is provided on any preservation activities that will occur within a selected repository. If data is not deposited into a repository, or if the selected repository does not offer preservation services, details are provided on any processes used for data cleaning and/or format changes, including any file format considerations to ensure long term availability (e.g., proprietary/non-proprietary files, coding languages, scripts and/or programs and versions able to access the data).</p>		
			Subtotal: _____
			Total: _____